

Structural evaluation and Molecular docking analysis on 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one - Anti breast cancer activity

Dona Benny¹, Blessen P V², Amala Rose Augustine³,

¹ *Department of Physics, Acharya Institute of Technology, Bengaluru,560107*

² *Department of Physics, Vel Tech Rangarajan Dr.Sagunthala R&D Institute of Science and Technology, Avadi,
Chennai*

³ *Department of education, Regional Institute of Educatio, Mysore*

Abstract

In this research, phyto compound 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one was theoretically evaluated using Density Functional Theory to fully understand structural features and vibrational modes of title compound. TD – DFT technique is employed in UV-Visible analysis is done on 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one. Frontier Molecular Orbitals are analyzed and values of global molecular reactivity descriptors are calculated. Regions with affinity to electron and nucleus are plotted through MEP. Multiwfn 3.8 software has been employed in analysis of topology to detect the principal bonding areas and regions of weak interactions. NBO and NLO analysis was employed using DFT. Evaluation of biological aspects of the compound to examine its therapeutic significance was carried out through measuring drug likeness parameters and molecular docking studies. Molecular docking with target protein to study anti-breast cancer capabilities of 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one is done using Autodock tools and docked confirmations are visualized through Discovery Studio.

KEYWORDS: DFT, Vibrational analysis, NBO, NLO, MOLECULAR DOCKING

Introduction

Complex organic substances called phyto compounds are present in plants. Given their potential for disease prevention, they are employed in drug development. Isoflavones is a class of phyto compounds under research for their potential medicinal applications [1,2]. 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one (IUPAC name) is a Methoxyisoflavone which falls under this subcategory. Title compound has 34 atoms and empirical formula is C₁₇H₁₄O₃. Molecular weight of title compound is 266.29g. It is found to be soluble in Chloroform, Dichloromethane, Ethyl Acetate, Acetone, etc. Title compound appears as white powder.

Breast cancer is one of the conditions that affect women most frequently. According to researchers, different stages of breast cancer account for 30% of all reported malignancies among women [3]. Primary cause of mortality from cancer is metastatic cancer progression, which is mostly driven by cell migration. The ineffectiveness of currently available chemotherapeutic medications to eradicate or cure metastasis highlights need of novel therapies [4, 5]. Due to their broad safety profile, capacity to destroy cancer stem cells as well as a variety of cancer cell types, and critical signaling pathways, naturally occurring substances, primarily phytochemicals, have attention in cancer treatment in recent times [6]. Anti-cancer property of Isoflavone depends on the

pharmacokinetic properties of it. Clinical studies claims that genistein and daidzein can prevent prostate cancer, breast cancer and cardiovascular diseases [7]. Breast cancer cells death can be induced with genistein. Along with antioxidative activity of isoflavone, it is having anti breast cancer effect and anticancer effect on uterine also [8].

On understanding the scope and biological activity of title compound, it is explored in this present research. 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one is a phytochemical which is not evaluated for its pharmaceutical applications. DFT or molecular docking studies of title compound are not reported till date [9-26]. Hence an attempt is made to analyze title compound using DFT Studies. The primary focus of this work includes structural evaluation, study of electron distribution, vibrational analysis and measuring biological activity of 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one. Evaluation of molecular geometry comprising of measuring bond parameters are done. Spectroscopic evaluations and UV-Visible spectroscopy are performed theoretically in gas phase. Distribution of electronic charges and other surface features are examined using MEP, ELF and LOL maps. To investigate electron density and interactions, NBO analysis is used. Optical properties of title compound are analyzed through NLO. Biological aspects are measured by drug likeness evaluation through Swiss ADME platform. 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one was docked for protein 4i8v and binding energy value is obtained indicating the effectiveness of the title compound to fight breast cancer.

COMPUTATIONAL METHODS

Chosen title compound 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one is subjected to analysis using Gaussian 16 W software [27]. Optimized structure is obtained by using Chemcraft [28]. Functional B3LYP is used in DFT analysis and 6 - 311G + + (d, p) is the basis set [29]. Bond characteristics were analyzed. In VEDA program [30,31], the vibrational assignment of the title chemical was obtained and ORIGIN 9.0 was utilized to map vibrational peaks. ELF, LOL diagrams were generated using MULTIWFN software [32]. In GAUSSUM program, Utilizing the TD-DFT approach, UV analysis was performed. NBO, NLO analysis has been done employing Gaussian. AUTODOCK TOOLS are used in performing molecular docking for 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one with chosen protein [33,34]. Utilizing SWISSADME software, the title compound's drug likeness qualities were examined and compared with standard values. Discovery Studio [35] was employed in generating the target protein which was selected with the analysis of bioactivity values obtained from PASS online tool [36].

OPTIMIZED GEOMETRY

Bond parameters and optimized structure of phytochemical 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one is given in Figure 1 and table 1. Geometric parameters are crucial in theoretical analysis as they assist in determining a molecule's stability [37]. Highest bond angle of magnitude 125.3° is between O1-C13-C7. H33-C20-H34 is having least bond angle- 109.4° . O-C bond has Average bond length 1.346\AA . Average bond length for C - C homonuclear bond is 1.413. Smallest bond length that exists between C9-H21 and C15-H27 is equal to 1.081\AA . Highest bond length of value 1.509\AA exists between C5 and C14.

Fig 1. Optimized geometric structure of 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one

*Table 1 Optimized geometrical structural parameters for title compound with
B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level*

Parameter Bond length(Å)	B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)	Parameter Bond angle(°)	B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)
O1-C6	1.371	C6-O1-C13	119.4
O1-C13	1.349	O1-C6-C4	121.6
O2-C11	1.358	O1-C6-C10	114.9
O2-C20	1.425	O1-C13-C7	125.3
O3-C8	1.227	O1-C13-H23	110.8
C4-C5	1.422	C11-O2-C20	119.2
C4-C6	1.409	O2-C11-C9	124.2
C4-C8	1.479	O2-C11-C10	115.9
C5-C9	1.392	O2-C20-H32	111.3
C5-C14	1.509	O2-C20-H33	111.4
C6-C10	1.387	O2-C20-H34	105.6
C7-C8	1.482	O3-C8-C4	123.1
C7-C12	1.484	O3-C8-C7	121.7
C7-C13	1.349	C5-C4-C6	117.3
C9-C11	1.404	C5-C4-C8	123.3

Parameter Bond length(Å)	B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)	Parameter Bond angle(°)	B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)
C9-H21	1.081	C4-C5-C9	119.3
C10-C11	1.389	C4-C5-C14	122.6
C10-H22	1.082	C6-C4-C8	119.4
C12-C15	1.403	C4-C6-C10	123.5
C12-C16	1.403	C4-C8-C7	115.2
C13-H23	1.082	C9-C5-C14	118.0
C14-H24	1.092	C5-C9-C11	121.6
C14-H25	1.091	C5-C9-H21	118.3
C14-H26	1.091	C5-C14-H24	110.0
C15-C17	1.392	C5-C14-H25	111.4
C15-H27	1.081	C5-C14-H26	111.4
C16-C18	1.393	C6-C10-C11	118.4
C16-H28	1.085	C6-C10-H22	120.6
C17-C19	1.395	C8-C7-C12	121.3
C17-H29	1.084	C8-C7-C13	119.0
C18-C19	1.393	C12-C7-C13	119.6
C18-H30	1.084	C7-C12-C15	121.3
C19-H31	1.084	C7-C12-C16	120.3
C20-H32	1.094	C7-C13-H23	123.9
C20-H33	1.095	C11-C9-H21	120.1
C20-H34	1.088	C9-C11-C10	119.9
		C11-C10-H22	121.0
		C15-C12-C16	118.5
		C12-C15-C17	120.5
		C12-C15-H27	119.5
		C12-C16-C18	120.9
		C12-C16-H28	119.5
		H24-C14-H25	109.1

Parameter <i>Bond length</i> (Å)	B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)	Parameter <i>Bond angle</i> (°)	B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)
		H24-C14-H26	109.1
		H25-C14-H26	105.7
		C17-C15-H27	120.0
		C15-C17-C19	120.5
		C15-C17-H29	119.5
		C18-C16-H28	119.5
		C16-C18-C19	120.1
		C16-C18-H30	119.7
		C19-C17-H29	120.0
		C17-C19-C18	119.5
		C17-C19-H31	120.3
		C19-C18-H30	120.2
		C18-C19-H31	120.2
		H32-C20-H33	109.7
		H32-C20-H34	109.4
		H33-C20-H34	109.4

Vibrational Analysis

Fourier Transform Infrared and Fourier Transform Raman spectra provide insights into a molecule's spectral bands at specific wavenumbers. Vibrational analysis is used in determining vibrational modes and their accompanying observable bands [38]. The findings are shown in Table 2. Maximum fundamentally active nonlinear modes that can be observed $3N - 6$ [39]. In 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one, which possess 34 atoms, there are 96 vibrational modes. Figure 2a and 2b display vibrational spectra.

C- H Vibrations: C- H vibrations are typically identified in $3000-3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region [40]. In 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one, peaks associated with C-H vibrations range from 3214 to 3013 cm^{-1} . Specifically, peak is at 3111 cm^{-1} , 3076 cm^{-1} , 3042 cm^{-1} correspond to pure C-H stretching with 100% vibrational assignments.

C- C Vibrations: In the context of aromatic rings, the characteristic wavenumber region for C-C vibrations typically spans from 1300 to 1000 cm^{-1} [41]. Upon analysis of the spectrum, eight

distinct peaks identified at 1658 Wavenumber cm^{-1} , 1643 cm^{-1} , 1640 cm^{-1} , 1590 cm^{-1} , 1333 cm^{-1} , 1315 cm^{-1} , 1058 cm^{-1} , 999 cm^{-1} . Additionally, some of these peaks exhibit partial C-C stretching contributions.

C- O Vibrations: Carbonyl bond is anticipated to visible in wavenumber range 1750-1600 cm^{-1} [42]. In our analysis, contributions associated with C-O vibrations were 1691 cm^{-1} and 1092 cm^{-1} . It should be noted that there are also partial contributions from other wavenumbers in this context.

Fig 2(a) FT-IR spectrum

Fig 2(b) FT-RAMAN spectrum

Table 2 FT-IR, FT-RAMAN vibrational data and computed vibrational wave numbers along with assignments of vibrational modes based on PED results

Modes	Frequency (cm^{-1})		IR Intensity		Raman activity		Vibrational Assignment PED%
	Unscaled	Scaled	Rel	Abs	Rel	Abs	
96	3214	3088	0	0	95	20	γ CH (98)
95	3213	3087	2	0	79	17	γ CH (95)
94	3212	3086	6	1	104	22	γ CH (98)
93	3203	3078	8	2	96	20	γ CH (99)
92	3187	3062	23	7	314	68	γ CH (90)
91	3176	3052	24	7	79	17	γ CH (98)
90	3166	3042	3	0	114	24	γ CH (95)
89	3159	3035	2	0	28	6	γ CH (99)
88	3139	3016	21	6	167	36	γ CH (91)

Modes	Frequency (cm^{-1})		IR Intensity		Raman activity		Vibrational Assignment PED%
	Unscaled	Scaled	Rel	Abs	Rel	Abs	
87	3111	2989	22	6	67	14	γ CH (100)
86	3107	2985	5	1	53	11	γ CH (99)
85	3076	2956	31	9	60	13	γ CH (100)
84	3042	2923	25	7	197	42	γ CH (100)
83	3013	2895	57	18	191	41	γ CH (91)
82	1691	1625	250	79	193	41	γ OC (72)
81	1658	1593	256	81	461	100	γ CC (46)
80	1643	1578	316	100	20	4	γ CC (55)
79	1640	1576	6	1	267	57	γ CC (39)
78	1613	1550	1	0	13	2	γ CC(44)+ β CCC(10)
77	1590	1527	64	20	38	8	γ CC (45)
76	1526	1466	14	4	13	2	β HCC (62)
75	1512	1453	0	0	21	4	β HCC(16)+ β HCH(11) + β CCO(16)
74	1503	1444	81	25	6	1	β HCH(77)+ τ HCOC(10)
73	1494	1435	9	2	16	3	β HCH(76)+ τ HCOC(16)
72	1490	1431	61	19	8	1	β HCH(47)
71	1476	1418	2	0	7	1	β HCH (60)
70	1474	1416	9	2	3	0	γ CC(10)+ β HCC(49)
69	1471	1413	8	2	7	1	β HCH(80)+ τ HCCC(11)
68	1435	1379	81	25	2	0	γ CC(13)+ β HCC(17)
67	1420	1364	7	2	11	2	β HCH (77)
66	1390	1335	131	41	17	3	β OCC (20)
65	1376	1322	35	11	1	0	γ OC(11)+ β HCO(43)
64	1354	1301	4	1	5	1	β HCC(52)
63	1333	1281	69	21	8	1	γ CC (17)
62	1315	1263	7	2	1	0	γ CC (56)
61	1305	1254	188	59	287	62	γ OC(15)+ γ CC(12)+ β HCO(16)

Modes	Frequency (cm^{-1})		IR Intensity		Raman activity		Vibrational Assignment PED%
	Unscaled	Scaled	Rel	Abs	Rel	Abs	
60	1278	1228	164	51	12	2	γ OC(10)+ γ CC(17)+ β HCC(20)
59	1239	1190	274	86	24	5	γ OC(19)+ β HCC(27)
58	1210	1162	0	0	13	2	BHCH(11)+ τ HCOC(46)
57	1207	1159	8	2	7	1	β HCC(74)
56	1203	1156	20	6	13	2	γ CC(29)+ β HCC(16)+ τ HCOC(10)
55	1182	1135	0	0	5	1	β HCC(76)
54	1166	1120	0	0	2	0	β HCH(29)+ τ HCOC(70)
53	1155	1109	137	43	8	1	γ OC(40)+ β HCC(19)
52	1104	1060	5	1	0	0	γ CC(35)+ β HCC(38)
51	1092	1049	40	12	2	0	γ OC(19)
50	1058	1016	11	3	1	0	γ CC(14)
49	1054	1012	2	0	0	0	β HCH(26)+ τ HCCC(56)
48	1042	1001	2	0	2	0	γ OC(16)+ β HCC(10) + τ HCCC(22)
47	1034	993	19	6	25	5	γ OC(11)+ β CCC(11)
46	1016	976	0	0	85	18	γ CC(24)+ β CCC(59)
45	1001	961	0	0	3	0	τ HCCC(71)+ τ CCCC(11)
44	999	960	24	7	7	1	γ CC(27)
43	982	943	0	0	1	0	τ HCCC(91)
42	959	921	2	0	26	5	γ OC(45)+ β CCC(10)
41	933	896	0	0	1	0	τ HCOC(40)+ τ HCCC(41)
40	918	882	12	3	5	1	τ HCOC(60)
39	877	842	22	6	20	4	β COC(16)
38	855	821	34	10	0	0	τ HCCC(67)+ α OCCC(16)
37	850	816	1	0	3	0	τ HCCC (98)
36	848	814	6	1	0	0	τ HCCC (67)
35	811	779	14	4	2	0	α OCCC(51)+ α CCCC(14)

Modes	Frequency (cm^{-1})		IR Intensity		Raman activity		Vibrational Assignment PED%
	Unscaled	Scaled	Rel	Abs	Rel	Abs	
34	793	762	3	0	30	6	β COC(17)
33	765	735	31	9	2	0	τ HCCC(21)+ τ CCCC(18)
32	708	680	44	13	0	0	τ HCCC (11)+ τ HCCC(26)+ α CCOC(26)
31	703	675	3	0	2	0	τ HCCC(38)+ τ CCCC(54)
30	682	655	2	0	8	1	β CCC(21)
29	643	617	1	0	0	0	τ HCCC(11)+ α OCCC(47) + α CCOC (12)
28	634	609	0	0	4	0	β CCC(77)
27	618	593	2	0	1	0	β CCC(10)+ β CCO(13)+ β OCC(11)
26	594	570	28	8	5	1	γ OC(10)+ β CCC(18)+ β COC(16)
25	575	552	2	0	1	0	τ CCCC(12)+ α CCCC(26)
24	571	548	25	7	13	2	γ CC(10)+ β CCC(10)
23	534	513	9	2	2	0	β CCC(21)+ α CCCC(13)
22	525	504	3	0	1	0	β CCC(16)
21	506	486	3	0	1	0	α CCCC(10)
20	445	427	0	0	1	0	τ COCC(21)
19	416	399	0	0	3	0	τ HCCC(10)+ τ CCCC(62)
18	398	382	3	0	2	0	β CCC(13)+ τ OCCC(17)+ τ COCC(16)
17	397	381	2	0	3	0	β CCC(22)+ β COC(35)
16	365	350	0	0	3	0	β OCC(21)+ β CCC(11)
15	327	314	5	1	0	0	β CCC(28)
14	299	287	1	0	1	0	τ HCOC(10)+ α CCCC(23)
13	261	250	0	0	3	0	β CCO(10)+ β COC(11)
12	240	230	0	0	1	0	τ CCCO(11)+ τ CCCC(11)+ τ COCC(12)
11	228	219	0	0	1	0	τ HCOC(44)+ α CCCC(19)

Modes	Frequency (cm^{-1})		IR Intensity		Raman activity		Vibrational Assignment PED%
	Unscaled	Scaled	Rel	Abs	Rel	Abs	
10	224	215	0	0	2	0	γ CC(16)+ β OCC(14)+ β COC(13)
9	207	198	0	0	0	0	τ HCCC(44)+ τ CCCO(12)
8	191	183	3	0	1	0	β OCC(37)+ β COC(18)
7	179	172	0	0	0	0	τ CCCC(25)+ α CCCC(21)
6	145	139	0	0	1	0	β CCC(12)+ τ CCOC(18)+ τ OCCC(15)
5	90	86	6	1	1	0	τ CCCO(17)+ τ COCC(29)
4	75	72	1	0	2	0	β CCC(33)+ α CCCC(24)
3	66	63	0	0	1	0	τ CCCC(31)+ τ CCOC(19)
2	46	44	0	0	6	1	τ CCCC (65)
1	29	27	1	0	0	0	τ CCOC(38)+ τ CCCO(10)+ τ OCCC (24)

NBO Analysis

NBO analysis is to translate solutions of Schrödinger's wave equation obtained from computational methods into understandable chemical bonding concepts [43]. NBO analysis facilitates the exploration of charge transfer, as well as intra- and intermolecular bonding [44]. It has proven its efficacy in interpreting hyper conjugative interactions and a phenomenon known as "delocalization" [45].

The transfer of charge between the antibonding orbitals of proton donors and lone pairs of proton acceptors is particularly significant in NBO analysis. Stabilization energy $-E_2$ associated with delocalization from donor (i) to acceptor O(j) is expressed as follows [46].

$$E_2 = q_i \cdot q_j \cdot (F(i, j) \cdot (\epsilon_i - \epsilon_j))$$

Here, q_i represents occupancy of donor orbital. $F(i, j)$ is off-diagonal Fock matrix element, ϵ_j and ϵ_i are diagonal elements [47]. Tendency for electron donation between donors and acceptors increases with higher E_2 values [48].

DFT and the second-order Fock matrix approach were used for NBO study. Table 3 presents the outcomes. The highest hyper conjugative interaction energy was observed for C18-C19 with C4, with 11128.3 kcal/mol, while lowest interaction energy occurred for C18-C19 with C15-H27 (36 kcal/mol). The maximum occupancy of the donor atom was found to be 1.99459.

Table 3 Second order perturbation theory analysis of Fock matrix in NBO basis for title compound

DONOR(i)	TYPE	ED/e	ACCEPTOR(j)	TYPE	ED/e	E(2) kcal/mol	E(j)-E(i) a.u.	F(i,j) a.u.
C 18 - C 19	π^*	0.33504	C 4	LP (1)	1.10157	11128.3	10.51	11.389
C 4	LP (1)	1.10157	C 20 - H 32	σ^*	0.01766	5943.07	4.64	6.267
C 20 - H 34	σ	1.99102	C 20 - H 33	σ^*	0.01771	4521.99	0.29	1.021
C 18 - C 19	π^*	0.33504	C 18 - H 30	σ^*	0.01373	4281.59	8.38	12.804
C 20 - H 34	σ	1.99102	C 18 - C 19	σ^*	0.01631	2885.86	0.13	0.549
O 3	LP (2)	1.88503	C 20 - H 33	σ^*	0.01771	2491.83	1	1.445
C 4	LP (1)	1.10157	C 20 - H 33	σ^*	0.01771	1800.45	7.22	4.303
C 18 - C 19	π^*	0.33504	C 20 - H 32	σ^*	0.01766	1648.87	15.15	10.623
C 15 - C 17	σ	1.97595	C 20 - H 33	σ^*	0.01771	1594.85	1.01	1.134
O 3	LP (2)	1.88503	C 18 - C 19	σ^*	0.01631	881.48	0.84	0.789
C 12 - C 16	π	1.65482	C 20 - H 33	σ^*	0.01771	865.12	0.25	0.455
C 20 - H 32	σ	1.99459	C 20 - H 33	σ^*	0.01771	669.24	0.47	0.5
C 20 - H 33	σ	1.99459	C 20 - H 33	σ^*	0.01771	666.31	0.46	0.498
C 18 - C 19	π^*	0.33504	C 20 - H 33	σ^*	0.01771	654.51	17.73	7.241
C 12 - C 16	π	1.65482	C 18 - C 19	σ^*	0.01631	584.94	0.09	0.228
C 12 - C 16	π^*	0.36649	C 20 - H 33	σ^*	0.01771	562.2	0.1	0.476
C 4	LP (1)	1.10157	C 18 - C 19	σ^*	0.01631	547.4	7.07	2.348
C 15 - C 17	σ	1.97595	C 18 - C 19	σ^*	0.01631	438.48	0.85	0.547
C 4	LP (1)	1.10157	C 20 - H 34	σ^*	0.00878	387.68	8.58	2.186
C 20 - H 34	σ	1.99102	C 14 - H 24	σ^*	0.00871	345.57	0.45	0.354
C 20 - H 34	σ	1.99102	C 16 - H 28	σ^*	0.01419	293.96	0.51	0.345
O 3	LP (2)	1.88503	C 20 - H 34	σ^*	0.00878	270.89	2.36	0.734
C 20 - H 32	σ	1.99459	C 18 - C 19	σ^*	0.01631	267.81	0.31	0.257
C 20 - H 33	σ	1.99459	C 18 - C 19	σ^*	0.01631	265.9	0.31	0.256
O 3	LP (2)	1.88503	C 13 - H 23	σ^*	0.01846	208.21	1.19	0.455
C 20 - H 34	σ	1.99102	C 20 - H 34	σ^*	0.00878	207.61	1.65	0.522
O 3	LP (2)	1.88503	C 16 - H 28	σ^*	0.01419	205.5	1.22	0.458
O 3	LP (2)	1.88503	C 14 - H 24	σ^*	0.00871	205.18	1.17	0.449
C 4	LP (1)	1.10157	C 14 - H 24	σ^*	0.00871	185.87	7.39	1.404
C 18 - C 19	π^*	0.33504	C 18 - C 19	σ^*	0.01631	180.38	17.57	3.792
O 3	LP (2)	1.88503	C 16 - C 18	σ^*	0.01648	176.69	1.36	0.449

DONOR(i)	TYPE	ED/e	ACCEPTOR(j)	TYPE	ED/e	E(2) kcal/mol	E(j)-E(i) a.u.	F(i,j) a.u.
C 15 - C 17	σ	1.97595	C 20 - H 34	σ^*	0.00878	176.17	2.37	0.579
C 4	LP (1)	1.10157	C 16 - H 28	σ^*	0.01419	175.54	7.44	1.366
C 4	LP (1)	1.10157	C 13 - H 23	σ^*	0.01846	172.2	7.41	1.347
C 4	LP (1)	1.10157	C 16 - C 18	σ^*	0.01648	163.72	7.58	1.33
O 3	LP (2)	1.88503	C 12 - C 16	π^*	0.36649	155.37	0.9	0.358
C 20 - H 34	σ	1.99102	C 17 - C 19	σ^*	0.01639	152.73	0.74	0.3
C 20 - H 34	σ	1.99102	C 14 - H 25	σ^*	0.00833	150.63	0.62	0.273
C 4	LP (1)	1.10157	C 12 - C 16	π^*	0.36649	150.56	7.13	1.079
C 18 - C 19	π^*	0.33504	C 20 - H 34	σ^*	0.00878	131.39	19.09	3.41
C 15 - C 17	σ	1.97595	C 14 - H 24	σ^*	0.00871	130.59	1.18	0.351
O 3	LP (2)	1.88503	C 17 - C 19	σ^*	0.01639	126.65	1.45	0.392
C 14 - H 26	σ	1.97272	C 20 - H 33	σ^*	0.01771	125.52	0.44	0.211
C 4	LP (1)	1.10157	C 17 - C 19	σ^*	0.01639	124.93	7.67	1.169
C 15 - C 17	σ	1.97595	C 16 - H 28	σ^*	0.01419	120.38	1.23	0.344
O 3	LP (2)	1.88503	C 14 - H 25	σ^*	0.00833	112.32	1.33	0.355
O 3	LP (2)	1.88503	C 15 - H 27	σ^*	0.01333	111.5	1.34	0.354
C 13 - H 23	σ	1.97906	C 20 - H 33	σ^*	0.01771	108.99	0.51	0.21

Frontier Molecular Orbitals (FMO) Analysis

A molecule's chemical stability and reactivity are strongly influenced by band gap [49]. HOMO and LUMO are the Molecular orbitals. Global molecular reactivity characteristics are usefully described by energies of HOMO - LUMO. Results, as presented in Table 4, indicate that HOMO has value of -6.44752 eV, while LUMO is -1.82318 eV. HOMO LUMO energy gaps in gas phase, is studied in figure 3. Negative energy values signify the molecule's stable structure. The title compound's band gap is estimated 4.624339 eV. These HOMO, LUMO energy values is to calculate the electronegativity of molecule. Energy to expel an Electron from the HOMO is represented by Ionization potential (I), which is 6.447517 eV. Lower electron affinity (A) values (1.823177 eV) show that a compound is more ready to receive electrons and form bonds. The title compound's electrophilicity index, Chemical potential, Global hardness, Global softness, and Electronegativity are all calculated to be 4.135347, 2.31217, 0.216247, -4.13535, and 3.698062, respectively. The low value of chemical softness (0.216247) suggests low toxicity of 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one, while the high value of electrophilicity (3.698062) indicates its potential for exhibiting strong biological activity [50].

Fig 3. Frontier Molecular Orbitals for 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one.

Table 4 Calculated energy values for 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one

Parameter	GAS PHASE
HOMO (eV)	-6.448
LUMO (eV)	-1.823
Ionization potential	6.448
Electron affinity	1.823
Energy gap(eV)	4.624
Electronegativity	4.135
Chemical potential	-4.135
Chemical hardness	2.312
Chemical softness	0.216
Electrophilicity index	3.698

UV VISIBLE ANALYSIS

Theoretically, 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one's UV spectra was employed with TD DFT. This computational approach is to investigate excitation energies, absorbances, and electronic transitions, oscillator strengths, providing valuable insights into the compound's UV-absorbing properties [51]. Addition to simulating vertical transition energies, TD-DFT is used to compute optical spectra with vibrationally resolved information, determine excited state structures and emission wavelengths, estimate atomic point charges and dipole moments, and model photochemical reactions [52]. UV spectrum obtained for gas.TD-DFT is represented in Figure 4. Energy gap of HOMO - LUMO of 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one is 4.62434eV. Here wavelength v/s absorbance is plotted and resulting graphs are compared. Theoretical values obtained are given in table 5. Computed UV method gives three electronic transitions at 317.184nm, 304.599nm and 282.643nm with oscillator strength 0.005au, 0.0748au and 0.062au respectively. Results are illustrated in table 5.

Fig 4. UV-Vis Band gap energy for the title compound

Table 5 Theoretical UV-Vis band gap energy (E) and oscillator strength (f) for title compound

Wavelength $\lambda_{\max}(\text{nm})$	Energy (cm^{-1})	Oscillator strength (f)	Major contribution
317.184	31527.406	0.0005	H-4->LUMO (17%), H-2->LUMO (78%)
304.599	32829.991	0.0748	HOMO->LUMO (94%)
282.643	35380.316	0.0621	H-1->LUMO (76%), HOMO->L+1 (16%)

MOLECULAR ELECTROSTATIC POTENTIAL

MEP at specific location close to a molecule gives details on the total electrostatic impact brought on by the local charge distribution of electrons and nuclei. It has a close connection to Dipole moments, Electronegativity and chemical reactivity of molecule. [53]. It can be considered as a

map pointing at electron excess as well as electron deficient areas. Electron excess areas are called as nucleophilic sites and deficient areas as electrophilic sites.

Molecular Electrostatic Potential (MEP) is a method to easily observe molecules polarity. Negative electrostatic potential regions attract protons as they have concentrated electron density while positive regions repel protons as electron density is low there. Colours are used to show variations in electrostatic potential, with red denoting highest negative and blue denoting high positive potentials. The color green represents no potential [54]. The order of the colours on electrostatic potential scales commonly Red to Blue. 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one's molecular Electrostatic potential map was enhanced using GAUSS VIEW, shown in figure 5.

Potential for title compound varies from -5.760 to 5.760 eV. Hydrogen atoms such as H32, H33, H34 occupies blue region indicating nucleophilic sites. Most electrophilic region is near O₃.

Fig 5. Molecular Electrostatic Potential mapping of title compound.

ELF AND LOL ANALYSIS

Insights into the Electron Localization function and Localized Orbital locator maps are provided through Surface analysis. Maps show possibility in discovering an electron pair on a molecule's surface [55]. ELF, LOL studies share similar theoretical underpinning. While LOL becomes noticeable when localized orbitals overlap, leading sharp gradients of localized orbitals, ELF is particularly sensitive to electron pair density. [56,57]. Multiwfn 3.8 software is employed in generating map like visual representations. ELF and LOL maps generated are presented in the fig 6 for ELF and 7 for LOL. Blue color depicts high range of ELF and LOL whereas red color depicts low value. Electron localized region in a molecule is pointed by higher values of Electron Localization Function ranging from 0.8 to 1 Bohr. Smaller values of the same depicts delocalization regions within the molecule [58]. In ELF map obtained, regions of high bonding

and non-bonding localized electrons are found about Hydrogen atoms H34, H21, H24, H31 and delocalized electrons are around C20, C9, C5, C8, C4, O3, C19 represented blue in color.

The localized orbital locator (LOL) map is created, using a scale ranging from 0.0 to 0.8 in units of Bohr. In LOL, covalent regions indicated by red color are found in region between C8 and C4, C9 and C5, C5 and C14 having high LOL value and electron depletion regions are present around C20, C9, C5, C8, C4, C19 with low LOL values. White color in central region of atoms H21, H24 and H31 is due to electron density which exceeds peak value of color scale.

Fig 6. Electron Localization Function

Fig 7. Localized Orbital Locator

NLO PROPERTIES

In the field of optoelectronic applications, material's structure and optical properties are crucial [59,60]. The finite-field approach demonstrates responsiveness to an applied electric field in three major parameters, Polarizability and Hyperpolarizability, Electric Dipole moment. [61]. Non-Linear optical (NLO) parameters found and are tabulated in Table 6. Maximum dipole moment was found to be $-0.022851D$ in the z-direction, while the values in x, y directions were recorded as -1.1669814 and -0.3895474 , respectively. This is somewhat lesser than industrial standards ($1.741D$) which is of urea. Highest polarizability α was found to be of α_{xx} with value of 13.1071969 esu. First order hyperpolarizability β showed maximum value at 1138.936983 esu along β_{xxx} . From basis set, total first order hyperpolarizability was calculated as 9.1247×10^{-30} esu. Total polarizability was observed as 1.7100×10^{-25} esu.

Table 6 Calculated first order hyperpolarizability (β), polarizability(α), dipole moment

Parameter	B3LYP/6-311++G(D,P)	Parameter	B3LYP/6-311++G(D,P)
μ_x	-1.1669814	β_{xxx}	1138.936983
μ_y	-0.3895474	β_{xxy}	360.4284031
μ_z	-0.022851	β_{xyy}	-143.12658
μ (D)	1.230493776	β_{yyy}	-79.4548603
α_{xx}	13.1071969	β_{zxx}	21.0751818
α_{xy}	-5.9215538	β_{xyz}	-11.6586475
α_{yy}	-7.1856431	β_{zyy}	-9.5736025
α_{xz}	-7.3998133	β_{xzz}	14.2574598
α_{yz}	-0.8583113	β_{yzz}	26.8512945
α_{zz}	-2.460028	β_{zzz}	11.7396975
α (a.u)	1.153841933	β_{tot} (a.u)	1056.188134
α (e.s.u)	1.7100E-25	β_{tot} (e.s.u)	9.1247E-30
$\Delta\alpha$ (a.u)	29.21695525		
$\Delta\alpha$ (e.s.u)	4.3300E-24		

DRUG - LIKENESS PARAMETERS

Drug - likeness analysis used to determine a compound's potential drug-like features by taking into account a variety of pharmacophoric aspects [62]. A logP, PSA, molar refractivity, count of HBA, count of HBD, number of Hydrogen Bonds, and so forth are important metrics used to evaluate a compound's drug-likeness and given in table 7. Lipinski established a set of rules, which comprises five criteria to identify pharmacologically active compounds [63,64]. Number of HBA is three, whereas the number of hydrogen BD is zero in drug-likeness evaluation of the title compound. Upon evaluation, all parameters were found to fall within the appropriate range specified by these rules [65,66].

Table 7 Drug likeness parameters of title compound

Descriptor	Value	Desirable range
H-bond donor (HBD)	0	≤ 5
H-bond acceptors (HBA)	3	≤ 10

MLogP	2.16	<4.15
Molar refractivity	79.58 g/mol	40-130
Molecular weight	266.29 g/mol	≤500 g/mol
No of atoms	34	About 50
Number of rotatable bonds	2	≤10

MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES

Assessing ligand receptor interactions and binding affinities against a specific receptor is done via molecular docking [67]. Docking parameters are evaluated to assess anti-breast cancer activity of title compound by docking it into active sites of target protein. Target protein with anti-breast cancer activity (4i8v) from protein data bank is chosen. Molecular docking was done with the software AutoDock 1.5.6 tools graphical user interface and docking parameters obtained are tabulated in table 8.

Inhibition constant (K_i) of compound was studied with the help of binding energy using,

$$K_i = \exp (\Delta G / RT)$$

R the universal gas constant, ΔG stands for the binding energy, and T stands for temperature. [68]. The docked conformations were visualized using PyMOL and are depicted in Figure 8 (a) and 8 (b). Docking between title compound and the 4i8v protein yielded favourable results, with Binding Energy of -8.24 kcal/mol. Reference RMSD value of 86.460 Å. Notably, the binding energy of Genistein, an active compound for breast cancer, was calculated to be -6.29 kcal/mol [69]. Binding energy values of title compound and genistein are comparable. Molecular docking results suggests that the title compound is potent in treating breast cancer.

Table 8 Docking parameters of 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one docked into active sites

<i>Protein (PDB ID)</i>	<i>Bonded residues</i>	<i>Bonded distance(A)</i>	<i>Type of interaction</i>	<i>Estimated inhibition constant (nM)</i>	<i>Binding energy (kcal/mol)</i>	<i>vsW+ Hbond+ desolv (kcal/mol)</i>	<i>Reference RMSD (A)</i>
(4i8v)	B: ILE386	1.84978	Conventional H bond	910.06	-8.24	-8.73	86.460
	UNK0:C	3.85605	Alkyl				
	UNK0:C	3.63647	Alkyl				
	UNK0:C	4.64918	Alkyl				
	UNK0	4.26025	Pi- Alkyl				

	UNKO	4.3793	Pi- Alkyl
	UNKO	4.5161	Pi- Alkyl
	UNKO	5.48433	Pi- Alkyl
	UNKO	5.17783	Pi- Alkyl

Fig 8 Docking conformation of 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one with (4i8v)

CONCLUSION

Density Functional Theory analysis of 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one was performed to yield optimized geometrical arrangement and various bond parameters were calculated. 96 normal modes of title compound were computed for FT IR, FT Raman. Natural bonding orbital analysis indicated Charge transfer mechanisms and also interactions existing between donor and acceptor atoms. From value of energies of the HOMO, LUMO obtained from FMO analysis, the values of reactivity descriptors were calculated. UV-Vis spectra obtain using TD-DFT technique. A map of electrophilic and nucleophilic regions of the compound was obtained through MEP analysis. Distribution of electrons and present interactions were analyzed employing ELF and LOL analysis. MEP, ELF, LOL maps are created. Hyperpolarizability and polarizability is determined using NLO analysis. Drug likeness parameters were obtained to be satisfying Lipinski's rule of five. Docking was performed with 4i8v protein using 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one as ligand, which gives binding energy of -8.24 kcal / mol. Molecule in consideration would be utilized as breast cancer treatment, where 7-methoxy-5-methyl-3-phenylchromen-4-one is a potent compound.

REFERENCES

- [1] Altaf, A.A., Kausar, S. and Badshah, A., 2018. Spectral calculations with DFT. *Density Functional Calculations: Recent Progresses of Theory and Application*, 101.[2]
- [2] Honenberg, P. and Kohn, W., 2017. Inhomogeneous electron gas. *RESONANCE-JOURNAL OF SCIENCE EDUCATION*, 22(8), pp.810-811.

- [3] Akhtar Siddiqui, J., Singh, A., Chagtoo, M., Singh, N., Madhav Godbole, M. and Chakravarti, B., 2015. Phytochemicals for breast cancer therapy: current status and future implications. *Current cancer drug targets*, 15(2), pp.116-135.
- [4] Ferlay, J., Héry, C., Autier, P. and Sankaranarayanan, R., 2010. Global burden of breast cancer. *Breast cancer epidemiology*, pp.1-19.
- [5] Ham, S.L., Nasrollahi, S., Shah, K.N., Soltisz, A., Paruchuri, S., Yun, Y.H., Luker, G.D., Bishayee, A. and Tavana, H., 2015. Phytochemicals potentially inhibit migration of metastatic breast cancer cells. *Integrative Biology*, 7(7), pp.792-800.
- [6] Dandawate, P.R., Subramaniam, D., Jensen, R.A. and Anant, S., 2016, October. Targeting cancer stem cells and signaling pathways by phytochemicals: Novel approach for breast cancer therapy. In *Seminars in cancer biology* (Vol. 40, pp. 192-208). Academic Press.
- [7] Vitale, D. C., Piazza, C., Melilli, B., Drago, F., & Salomone, S. (2013). Isoflavones: estrogenic activity, biological effect and bioavailability. *European journal of drug metabolism and pharmacokinetics*, 38, 15-25.
- [8] Takashima, M., Nara, K., Niki, E., Yoshida, Y., Hagihara, Y., Stowe, M., & Horie, M. (2013). Evaluation of biological activities of a groundnut (*Apios americana* Medik) extract containing a novel isoflavone. *Food chemistry*, 138(1), 298-305.
- [9] Leela, J.S.P.P., Hemamalini, R., Muthu, S. and Al-Saadi, A.A., 2015. Spectroscopic investigation (FTIR spectrum), NBO, HOMO–LUMO energies, NLO and thermodynamic properties of 8-Methyl-N-vanillyl-6-nonenamide by DFT methods. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 146, pp.177-186.
- [10] AlRabiah, H., Muthu, S., Al-Omary, F., Al-Tamimi, A.M., Raja, M., Muhamed, R.R. and El-Emam, A.A.R., 2017. Molecular structure, vibrational spectra, NBO, Fukui function, HOMO-LUMO analysis and molecular docking study of 6-[(2-methylphenyl) sulfanyl]-5-propylpyrimidine-2, 4 (1H, 3H)-dione. *Macedonian Journal of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering*, 36(1), pp.59-80.
- [11] Muthu, S. and Porchelvi, E.E., 2013. FTIR, FT-RAMAN, NMR, spectra, normal co-ordinate analysis, NBO, NLO and DFT calculation of N, N-diethyl-4-methylpiperazine-1-carboxamide molecule. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 115, pp.275-286.
- [12] Kuruvilla, T.K., Prasana, J.C., Muthu, S., George, J. and Mathew, S.A., 2018. Quantum mechanical and spectroscopic (FT-IR, FT-Raman) study, NBO analysis, HOMO-LUMO, first order hyperpolarizability and molecular docking study of methyl [(3R)-3-(2-methylphenoxy)-3-phenylpropyl] amine by density functional method. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 188, pp.382-393.
- [13] Fernandez, M.V.G., Rajamannana, B., Periandyb, S. and Soundharyab, M.S., 2021. DFT AND SPECTROSCOPIC ANALYSIS OF P-BROMO-DL-PHENYLALANINE.

- [14] George, J., Prasana, J.C., Muthu, S., Kuruvilla, T.K., Sevanti, S. and Saji, R.S., 2018. Spectroscopic (FT-IR, FT Raman) and quantum mechanical study on N-(2, 6-dimethylphenyl)-2-{4-[2-hydroxy-3-(2-methoxyphenoxy) propyl] piperazin-1-yl} acetamide. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1171, pp.268-278.
- [15] Furer, V.L., Borisoglebskaya, E.I., Zverev, V.V. and Kovalenko, V.I., 2006. DFT and IR spectroscopic analysis of p-tert-butylthiacalix [4] arene. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 63(1), pp.207-212.
- [16] Ali, M., Mansha, A., Asim, S., Zahid, M., Usman, M. and Ali, N., 2018. DFT Study for the Spectroscopic and Structural Analysis of p-Dimethylaminoazobenzene. *Journal of Spectroscopy*, 2018.
- [17] George, J., Prasana, J.C., Muthu, S., Kuruvilla, T.K. and Saji, R.S., 2020. Evaluation of vibrational, electronic, reactivity and bioactivity of propafenone—A spectroscopic, DFT and molecular docking approach. *Chemical data collections*, 26, p.100360.
- [18] Santhy, K.R., Sweetlin, M.D., Muthu, S., Kuruvilla, T.K. and Abraham, C.S., 2019. Structure, spectroscopic study and DFT calculations of 2, 6 bis (tri fluoro methyl) benzoic acid. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1177, pp.401-417.
- [19] Kuruvilla, T.K., Prasana, J.C., Muthu, S. and George, J., 2017. Quantum Mechanical Calculations and Spectroscopic (FT-IR, FT Raman) Investigation on 1-cyclohexyl-1-phenyl-3-(piperidin-1-yl) propan-1-ol, by density functional method. *Int. J. Mater. Sci.*, 12(2), pp.282-301.
- [20] Yıldırım, A.Ö., Yıldırım, M.H. and Kaştaş, Ç.A., 2016. Studies on the synthesis, spectroscopic analysis and DFT calculations on (E)-4, 6-dichloro-2-[(2-chlorophenylimino) methyl]-3-methoxyphenol as a novel Schiff's base. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1113, pp.1-8.
- [21] Shaji, D., 2018. Molecular docking studies of human MCT8 protein with soy isoflavones in Allan-Herndon-Dudley syndrome (AHDS). *Journal of pharmaceutical analysis*, 8(5), pp.318-323.
- [22] Ribaldo, G., Ongaro, A., Zagotto, G., Memo, M. and Gianoncelli, A., 2021. Evidence on selective binding to G-quadruplex DNA of isoflavones from *Maclura pomifera* by mass spectrometry and molecular docking. *Natural Product Research*, 35(15), pp.2583-2587.
- [23] Sathish, M., Rajasekaran, L., Shanthi, D., Kanagathara, N., Sarala, S. and Muthu, S., 2021. Spectroscopic (FT-IR, FT-Raman, UV-Vis) molecular structure, electronic, molecular docking, and thermodynamic investigations of indole-3-carboxylic acid by DFT method. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1234, p.130182.
- [24] Vennila, M., Rathikha, R., Muthu, S., Jeelani, A., Devi, R.N. and Irfan, A., 2022. Theoretical spectroscopic electronic elucidation with different solvents (IEFPCM model), biological assessment and molecular docking studies on Moroxydine-Antiviral drug agent. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 355, p.118946.

- [25] Anuradha, A., Saji, R.S., Varghese, M.G., Muthu, S. and Prasana, J.C., 2022. Vibrational spectroscopic, DFT studies and molecular docking on (2R)-2-acetamido-N-benzyl-3-methoxy propanamide as an antineuropathic pain drug. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 50, pp.2615-2622.
- [26] Ramana, P.V., Sundius, T., Muthu, S., Mouli, K.C., Krishna, Y.R., Prasad, K.V., Devi, R.N., Irfan, A. and Santhamma, C., 2022. Spectroscopic, quantum mechanical, electronic excitation properties (Ethanol solvent), DFT investigations and molecular docking analysis of an anti-cancer drug Bendamustine. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1253, p.132211.
- [27] Frisch, M.J., Trucks, G.W., Schlegel, H.B., Scuseria, G.E., Robb, M., Cheeseman, J.R., Scalmani, G., Barone, V.P.G.A., Petersson, G.A., Nakatsuji, H.J.R.A. and Li, X., 2016. Gaussian 16, Revision A. 03, Gaussian. Inc., Wallingford CT, 3.
- [28] *Graphical program for visualization of quantum chemistry computations- Chemcraft*. Available at: <https://www.chemcraftprog.com/>.
- [29] Costa Jr, A.C., Ondar, G.F., Versiane, O., Ramos, J.M., Santos, T.G., Martin, A.A., Raniero, L., Bussi, G.G.A. and Soto, C.T., 2013. DFT: B3LYP/6-311G (d, p) vibrational analysis of bis-(diethyldithiocarbamate) zinc (II) and natural bond orbitals. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 105, pp.251-258.
- [30] Jamróz, M.H., 2013. Vibrational energy distribution analysis (VEDA): scopes and limitations. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 114, pp.220-230.
- [31] Jamroz, M.H., 2004. Vibrational energy distribution analysis VEDA 4.
- [32] Lu, T. and Chen, F., 2012. Multiwfn: A multifunctional wavefunction analyzer. *Journal of computational chemistry*, 33(5), pp.580-592.
- [33] Morris, G.M., Huey, R., Lindstrom, W., Sanner, M.F., Belew, R.K., Goodsell, D.S. and Olson, A.J., 2009. AutoDock4 and AutoDockTools4: Automated docking with selective receptor flexibility. *Journal of computational chemistry*, 30(16), pp.2785-2791.
- [34] Morris, G.M., Goodsell, D.S., Halliday, R.S., Huey, R., Hart, W.E., Belew, R.K. and Olson, A.J., 1998. Automated docking using a Lamarckian genetic algorithm and an empirical binding free energy function. *Journal of computational chemistry*, 19(14), pp.1639-1662.
- [35] DeLano, W.L., 2002. Pymol: An open-source molecular graphics tool. *CCP4 Newsl. Protein Crystallogr*, 40(1), pp.82-92
- [36] Filimonov, D.A., Lagunin, A.A., Glorizova, T.A., Rudik, A.V., Druzhilovskii, D.S., Pogodin, P.V. and Poroikov, V.V., 2014. Prediction of the biological activity spectra of organic compounds using the PASS online web resource. *Chemistry of Heterocyclic Compounds*, 50, pp.444-457.
- [37] Sevvanthi, S., Muthu, S., Raja, M., Aayisha, S., & Janani, S. (2020). PES, molecular structure, spectroscopic (FT-IR, FT-Raman), electronic (UV-Vis, HOMOLUMO), quantum

chemical and biological (docking) studies on a potent membrane permeable inhibitor: dibenzoxepine derivative. *Heliyon*, 6(8), e04724.

[38] Clara, T.H., Muthu, S. and Prasana, J.C., 2022. Quantum mechanical, spectroscopic and docking studies of (2E)-1-(4-aminophenyl)-3-(4-benzyloxyphenyl)-prop-2-en-1-one Chalcone derivative by density functional theory—A prospective respiratory drug. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 50, pp.2816-2825.

[39] Muthu, S., Prasana, J.C., Abraham, C.S. and Raja, M., 2018. Spectroscopic (FT-IR, FT-Raman) investigation, topology (ESP, ELF, LOL) analyses, charge transfer excitation and molecular docking (dengue, HCV) studies on ribavirin. *Chemical Data Collections*, 17, pp.236-250

[40] Abraham, C.S., Prasana, J.C., Muthu, S. and Raja, M., 2018. Quantum computational studies, spectroscopic (FT-IR, FT-Raman and UV–Vis) profiling, natural hybrid orbital and molecular docking analysis on 2, 4 Dibromoaniline. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1160, pp.393-405

[41] Abraham, C.S., Prasana, J.C. and Muthu, S., 2017. Quantum mechanical, spectroscopic and docking studies of 2-amino-3-bromo-5-nitropyridine by density functional method. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 181, pp.153-163

[42] Sevvanthi, S., Muthu, S. and Raja, M., 2018. Molecular docking, vibrational spectroscopy studies of (RS)-2-(tert-butylamino)-1-(3-chlorophenyl) propan-1-one: A potential adrenaline uptake inhibitor. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1173, pp.251-260.

[43] Weinhold, Frank & Landis, Clark & Glendening, Eric. (2016). What is NBO analysis and how is it useful? *International Reviews in Physical Chemistry*. 35. 399-440. 10.1080/0144235X.2016.1192262.

[44] Weinhold, F. and Landis, C.R., 2005. *Valency and bonding: a natural bond orbital donor-acceptor perspective*. Cambridge University Press

[45] Yang, Y., Zhang, W. and Gao, X., 2006. Blue-shifted and red-shifted hydrogen bonds: Theoretical study of the CH₃CHO... HNO complexes. *International journal of quantum chemistry*, 106(5), pp.1199-1207.

[46] Oliaey, A.R., Shiroudi, A., Zahedi, E. and Deleuze, M.S., 2018. Theoretical study on the mechanisms and kinetics of the β -elimination of 2, 2-dihaloethyltrihalosilanes (X= F, Cl, Br) compounds: a DFT study along with a natural bond orbital analysis. *Reaction Kinetics, Mechanisms and Catalysis*, 124(1), pp.27-44.

[47] Miar, M., Shiroudi, A., Pourshamsian, K., Oliaey, A.R. and Hatamjafari, F., 2021. Theoretical investigations on the HOMO–LUMO gap and global reactivity descriptor studies, natural bond orbital, and nucleus-independent chemical shifts analyses of 3-phenylbenzo [d]

thiazole-2 (3 H)-imine and its para-substituted derivatives: Solvent and substituent effects.

Journal of Chemical Research, 45(1-2), pp.147-158

[48] Radder, S.B., Melavanki, R., Hiremath, S.M., Kusanur, R., Khemalpure, S.S. and Jeyaseelan, S.C., 2021. Synthesis, spectroscopic (FT-IR, FT-Raman, NMR & UV-Vis), reactive (ELF, LOL, Fukui), drug likeness and molecular docking insights on novel 4-[3-(3-methoxy-phenyl)-3-oxo-propenyl]-benzotrile by experimental and computational methods. *Heliyon*, 7(11), p.e08429.

[49] Fleming, I., 2011. *Molecular orbitals and organic chemical reactions*. John Wiley & Sons.

[50] Jebapriya, J.C., Prasana, J.C., Muthu, S. and Rizwana, B.F., 2022. Spectroscopic (FT-IR and FT-Raman), quantum computational (DFT) and molecular docking studies on 2 (E)-(4-N, N-dimethylaminobenzylidene)-5-methylcyclohexanone. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 50, pp.2695-2702.

[51] Runge, E. and Gross, E.K., 1984. Density-functional theory for time-dependent systems. *Physical review letters*, 52(12), p.997

[52] Laurent, A.D. and Jacquemin, D., 2013. TD-DFT benchmarks: a review. *International Journal of Quantum Chemistry*, 113(17), pp.2019-2039.

[53] Bendjeddou, A., Abbaz, T., Gouasmia, A. and Villemin, D., 2016. Molecular structure, HOMO-LUMO, MEP and Fukui function analysis of some TTF-donor substituted molecules using DFT (B3LYP) calculations. *Int. Res. J. Pure Appl. Chem*, 12(1), pp.1-9.

[54] Sethi, A. and Prakash, R., 2015. Novel synthetic ester of Brassicasterol, DFT investigation including NBO, NLO response, reactivity descriptor and its intramolecular interactions analyzed by AIM theory. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1083, pp.72-81.

[55] Prasana, J.C., Muthu, S. and Abraham, C.S., 2019. Molecular docking studies, charge transfer excitation and wave function analyses (ESP, ELF, LOL) on valacyclovir: a potential antiviral drug. *Computational biology and chemistry*, 78, pp.9-17.

[56] Silvi, B. and Savin, A., 1994. Classification of chemical bonds based on topological analysis of electron localization functions. *Nature*, 371(6499), pp.683-686.

[57] Jacobsen, H., 2008. Localized-orbital locator (LOL) profiles of chemical bonding. *Canadian Journal of Chemistry*, 86(7), pp.695-702

[58] Parakkal, S.C., Datta, R., Muthu, S., Irfan, A. and Jeelani, A., 2022. Computational investigation into structural, topological, electronic properties, and biological evaluation of spiro [1H-indole-3, 2'-3H-1, 3-benzothiazole]-2-one. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 359, p.119234.

[59] Labidi, N.S., Djebaili, A. and Rouina, I., 2011. Substitution effects on the polarizability (α) and first hyperpolarizability (β) of all-trans hexatriene. *Journal of Saudi Chemical Society*, 15(1), pp.29-37.

- [60] Kleinman, D.A., 1962. Nonlinear dielectric polarization in optical media. *Physical Review*, 126(6), p.1977
- [61] Manjusha, P., Prasana, J.C., Muthu, S. and Rizwana, B.F., 2020. Spectroscopic elucidation (FT-IR, FT-Raman and UV-visible) with NBO, NLO, ELF, LOL, drug likeness and molecular docking analysis on 1-(2-ethylsulfonylethyl)-2-methyl-5-nitro-imidazole: An antiprotozoal agent. *Computational Biology and Chemistry*, 88, p.107330.
- [62] Lipinski, C.A., 2004. Lead-and drug-like compounds: the rule-of-five revolution. *Drug discovery today: Technologies*, 1(4), pp.337-341
- [63] Lipinski, C.A., Lombardo, F., Dominy, B.W. and Feeney, P.J., 1997. Experimental and computational approaches to estimate solubility and permeability in drug discovery and development settings. *Advanced drug delivery reviews*, 23(1-3), pp.3-25.
- [64] Celik, S., Yurdakul, S. and Erdem, B., 2022. New silver (I) complex as antibiotic candidate: Synthesis, spectral characterization, DFT, QTAIM and antibacterial investigations and docking properties. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1261, p.132902
- [65] Brito, M.A.D., 2011. Pharmacokinetic study with computational tools in the medicinal chemistry course. *Brazilian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 47, pp.797-805.
- [66] Akare, U.R., Bandaru, S., Shaheen, U., Singh, P.K., Tiwari, G., Singare, P., Nayariseri, A. and Banerjee, T., 2014. Molecular docking approaches in identification of High affinity inhibitors of Human SMO receptor. *Bioinformation*, 10(12), p.737.
- [67] Sinha, C., Nischal, A., Pant, K.K., Bandaru, S., Nayariseri, A. and Khattri, S., 2014. Molecular docking analysis of RN18 and VEC5 in A3G-Vif inhibition. *Bioinformation*, 10(10), p.611.
- [68] Mumit, M.A., Pal, T.K., Alam, M.A., Islam, M.A.A.A.A., Paul, S. and Sheikh, M.C., 2020. DFT studies on vibrational and electronic spectra, HOMO–LUMO, MEP, HOMA, NBO and molecular docking analysis of benzyl-3-N-(2, 4, 5-trimethoxyphenylmethylene) hydrazinecarbodithioate. *Journal of molecular structure*, 1220, p.128715.
- [69] Mukund, V., Behera, S. K., Alam, A., & Nagaraju, G. P. (2019). Molecular docking analysis of nuclear factor- κ B and genistein interaction in the context of breast cancer. *Bioinformation*, 15(1), 11.